

**THE EFFECT OF VOLATILE CURE RESIDUALS ON THE GENERATION
OF THERMAL STRAIN AND TRANSVERSE MICROCRACKS IN PMR-15
CARBON FIBRE LAMINATES UNDER THERMAL CYCLING**

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ABSTRACT

Simultaneous thermogravimetric analysis with mass spectrometry of PMR-15 laminates which have been post-cured in the presence and absence of bagging films, demonstrates the entrapment of curing volatiles. These volatiles modify the thermomechanical response of the laminate leading to the enhancement of thermal strain and promote thermal microcracking. Furthermore, differing thermal degradation characteristics above 300°C suggest that longer polycyclopentadiene crosslinks exist in material post-cured in the autoclave bagging package. Differences in cure chemistry appear responsible for the varying thermomechanical and microcrack stability of the laminates.

1. INTRODUCTION

PMR-15 refers to a cyclopentadiene endcapped bismaleimide matrix system for carbon fibre composites based on the polymerisation of monomeric reactants. The ratio of the reactants has been designed to give good composite processing and the code number refers to the average molar mass of the prepolyimide formed initially during cure (1500g mol^{-1}).

During cure, additional polymerisation through the norbornene endcaps occurs involving a reverse Diels-Alder reaction. Ideally this occurs without the evolution of volatile reaction by-products but it is believed to involve copolymerisation of the maleimide with cyclopentadiene, formed in situ.

The system enables the convenient fabrication of composites with temperature resistance in excess of 300°C. In order to achieve this stability, similar curing and postcuring temperatures are required. On cooling from this elevated temperature, thermal strains develop within the composite. For a unidirectional

laminate they are present at the micromechanics level because of a mismatch in the thermal expansion coefficients of the fibre and matrix. For angle-ply laminates, they result from the mismatch in properties of the plies of differing orientation. These thermal strains can have a major effect on the overall mechanical performance of a cross-ply laminate and may approach first ply failure strain making the laminate more susceptible to transverse cracking (2).

It has been shown (2) that on cooling from a Temperature T_1 to a lower temperature T_2 the thermal strain which develops in the longitudinal direction of the transverse ply of a $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ composite, ϵ^{th} , is given by:

$$\epsilon^{th} = \frac{E_1 b (\alpha_t - \alpha_l) (T_1 - T_2)}{(E_1 b + E_t d)} \quad (1)$$

where E_1 and E_t are the Young's moduli of the unidirectional plies parallel to the fibres (the longitudinal or 0° direction, 1) and perpendicular to the fibres (the transverse or 90° direction, t) respectively. α_l , α_t , b and 2d are the linear expansion coefficients and thicknesses of the 0° and 90° plies respectively. T_1 is the strain free temperature.

To overcome uncertainty in the values of α_t , α_l and T_1 the radius of curvature (ρ) of an unbalanced cross-ply $0^\circ/90^\circ$ laminate can be used analogously to a bimetal strip. Thus:

$$(\alpha_t - \alpha_l)(T_1 - T_2) = \frac{(b + d)}{2\rho} + \frac{(E_1 b^3 + E_t d^3)}{6\rho(b + d)} \left[\frac{1}{E_1 b} + \frac{1}{E_t d} \right] \quad (2)$$

For continuous monitoring of ϵ^{th} , ρ can be calculated directly the displacement (δ) of the beam from flat (3).

One of the major problems associated with the application of this matrix system is the continuous development of matrix cracks in fabric based laminates during thermal cycling (4,5). In this paper, we explore the role of thermal strains in this phenomenon and demonstrate that the entrapment of curing volatiles plays a crucial part.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

All the $0_2^\circ/90_2^\circ$ laminates were prepared from PMR-15 Polyimide impregnated carbon fibre prepreg (BP Advanced Composites Ltd, Bristol, UK) using a pressclave technique with cure and post-cure cycles commonly used for the commercial manufacture with this material (5). Curing at 290° was followed by post-curing at 316°C (3 hrs). This was carried out either free, with the bagging films removed or still in place. The beams had fibre volume fractions of 0.6 ± 0.01 . Some beams were dried to constant weight in an air circulating oven, at 105°C , prior to conditioning in standard humidity tanks containing saturated salt solutions at 50°C of known moisture vapour pressure to constant weight. To assess the effect of entrapped

fabrication volatiles on the radius of curvature of the $0_2^\circ/90_2^\circ\text{C}$ beams they were previously dried in vacuum at 50°C to keep any thermal changes to a minimum. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) with simultaneous mass spectrometry was carried out on a Dupont 951 thermal balance linked to VG Quadrupoles micromass PC. Some TGA runs were carried out on a Stanton thermal balance. For sample protection, flowing Helium or Nitrogen were used, respectively. Some $0^\circ/90^\circ$ beams were subjected to repeated thermal cycling between 20 and 300°C in a custom built shock testing oven (Lenton Thermal Designs Ltd, UK). Between cycles the beams were weighed and their displacements recorded. Full experimental details have been given elsewhere (6).

Fig 1: The temperature dependence of the beam displacement, δ , of a freely bending $0_2^\circ/90_2^\circ$ PMR-15 CFRP laminate, (a) as manufactured, heated to post-cure temperature of 316°C (0.031%), (b) after drying in vacuo at 50°C for 4 weeks (0.093%), (c) as (a) but taken to T_1 at 365°C (0.041%), (d) as (b) but taken to T_1 at 343°C (0.11%). The figures in brackets are weight losses during one thermal cycle (a,c) or drying (b,d).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Residual Thermal Strains in As-fabricated Dried and Thermally Cycled Beams

The displacement of the post-cured $0_2^\circ/90_2^\circ$ beam, was monitored to the original post curing temperature of 316°C . As can be seen in Fig 1a, the coupon did not become flat demonstrating that the strain free temperature, T_1 in equation 1, had not been reached. T_1 is therefore surprisingly greater than the post-cure temperature and is reached some 50° higher at 365°C , as shown in Fig 1c. Of more interest, however, is the larger beam displacement, d , of the beams subjected to one thermal cycle. This increase manifests itself in an increase in residual strain in the equivalent balanced $0_2^\circ/90_4^\circ/0_2^\circ$ laminate from approximately 0.58% to 0.72%. This change in beam displacement was accompanied by a reduction in weight of 0.031%. For the beam heated to T_1 a weight loss of 0.041% was recorded. To establish the role of these occluded volatiles, the beams were 'dried' in vacuum, prior to a study of the beam displacement. As shown in Fig 1(b) and 1(d), the hysteresis has largely been removed by the drying procedure. However, some limited thermomechanical instability still existed in the beam which had only been cycled to the post cure temperature which indicated that some additional curing had occurred up to T_1 . This additional cure was accompanied by the generation of further volatiles as demonstrated by differing weight losses during cycling to the post-cure and strain-free temperatures (Fig 1a and 1c). The lower T_1 for the dried beam may also reflect a complex involvement of the volatiles in the generation of thermal strains.

3.2 Effect of Moisture on the Thermally Generated Strain

It is well-known that resin swelling by moisture ingress leads to a reduction in thermal strain (7). The effect of moisture swelling has been examined by equilibrating the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ beams at known humidities and recording the beam displacement. The results of these experiments are given in Fig 2. Also included in Fig 2 is the thermal strain of the as-fabricated beam with respect to the change in weight on drying. The curvature of the as-fabricated beam cannot be accounted for by matrix swelling as a result moisture ingress after curing. From this data the moisture swelling coefficient has been estimated and the results given elsewhere (6).

It has also been reported that some resins have moisture enhanced expansion coefficients which can give rise to higher residual strains on cooling. Careful examination of the linear transverse and matrix expansion coefficients demonstrated that, for the 316°C post-cured material, they are strongly temperature dependent below 200°C which might also be volatile dependent (6). If drying of the beam during the first cycle was the major mechanism operating, the reduced expansion coefficient should cause a reduction not an increase in thermal strain, as reported in Fig 1a. It is difficult to compare the results from individual beams in Fig 1 since slight variations in initial curvature were encountered, but experiments with the same beam demonstrated that a larger displacement always arose after thermal

Fig 2: The residual thermal strain in dried $0_2^{\circ}/90_4^{\circ}/0_2^{\circ}$ PMR-15 CFRP beams after being brought to equilibrium moisture content (●) compared to the as-fabricated beam containing residual volatiles (○).

Fig 3: Thermogravimetric analysis of PMR-15 CFRP beams post-cured (a) free (○), (b) bagged-up (●), (c) as (b) second cycle after cooling in nitrogen (■), (d) as (b) after storage in air for 12 hours (▲).

cycling.(6) As a result, a differing mechanism must be responsible for the effect of the volatiles on the residual thermal strain. The most likely explanation involves a reduction in strain-free temperature in the presence of occluded volatiles, but because of the high temperatures involved, it is not possible to detect this experimentally using the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ beam technique. A depression of the strain free temperature by $\approx 40^\circ\text{C}$ would be required but the actual value is difficult to estimate because of simultaneous variations in α_t and E_t .

3.2 Thermogravimetric Analysis

The experiments above, illustrate the need for full understanding of the nature of the volatiles released during thermal cycling. It is also clear from the form of the displacement-temperature curve near the strain free temperature in Fig 1 and the simultaneous loss in weight, that the additional cure may involve volatile formation. By comparing beams which have been post-cured (a) with the films in tact, and (b) free of the bagging films, it is possible to confirm the entrapment of volatiles during fabrication and to show that post-curing involves volatile loss and not just removal of moisture absorbed between curing and post-curing. The results of this experiment is given in Fig 3 where the thermogravimetric analysis shows weight losses up to the onset of degradation at 350°C of 0.5% and $\approx 0.2\%$ for cases (a) and (b) respectively. From a mass spectral analysis of the volatiles, the four regions of the thermogram of the material post-cured in the bag can be identified: the formation of (i) up to 100°C methanol with some water; (ii) $100\text{-}250^\circ\text{C}$ water by continued diffusion of water from the beam; (iii) carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide and some cyclopentadiene formation at the onset of degradation; (iv) above 350°C cyclopentadiene, carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide and hydrocarbon species as a result of thermal degradation.

For the freely post-cured material much of the methanol, water and some cyclopentadiene had already been removed during post-curing but the trends are similar. However, in region (iv) for the bagged material, the concentration of cyclopentadiene was 50 times greater.

Repetition of the TG analysis shows that the majority of the volatiles or degradation products are lost in the first thermal cycle and the onset of degradation is increased to $\approx 400^\circ\text{C}$. The removal of cyclopentadiene, therefore, involves a finite process, leading to greater thermal stability.

Since cyclopentadiene cannot be considered to be physically held in the matrix following the reverse Diels-Alder curing reaction below 300°C , it is concluded that this must arise from a degradation process. It follows therefore that the differing quantities desorbed from the bagged-up and freely post-cured beams, shown in Fig 4, arises from a chemically structural difference in the matrix. According to Wilson (1) the curing chemistry leads to an alternating copolymer of cyclopentadiene and the bismaleimide, in the formation of monomeric crosslinks. However, cyclic monomers have low ceiling temperatures above which they rather than their polymers are thermodynamically stable (8). Therefore the cyclopentadiene crosslinks will

probably be polymeric with a degree of polymerisation determined by the monomer concentration. As a result longer crosslinks will form in material post-cured in the bagging films where cyclopentadiene loss is restricted. These crosslinks will also tend to be unstable at high temperatures leading differing volatile composition (Fig 4) and an understandable thermal stability after one thermal cycle (Fig 3). Similar arguments will apply to freely post-cured thick laminates where cyclopentadiene diffusion is also restricted.

In addition observable moisture sorption occurred overnight unless the samples were stored in a dry atmosphere (as shown in Fig 3).

3.3 The Role of Volatiles and Thermal Strain Development on Microcrack Formation During Thermal Cycling

$0^\circ/90^\circ$ beams were weighed before and after a set number of thermal cycles from 20 to 300°C at 50K min^{-1} . The weight loss over 160 cycles was 0.5% for the dried material and about 1.3% for the as-post-cured laminates. The beam displacements were also monitored and the initial changes given in Fig 5 arise from desorption by the as-post-cured beam and absorption by the dried beam during the first cycle. For the dried beam the initial decline is caused by moisture ingress. After remaining constant for ≈ 25 cycles, it declines again monotonically following the trend in weight loss. For the as-fabricated beam, the initial displacement increases as the beam loses volatiles, reaching a plateau. After ≈ 50 cycles, it continues to decline similarly to the dried beam. The long-term decrease in displacements of both beams result from the formation of transverse cracks in the 90° ply. As can be seen in Table 1 the crack densities after 160 cycles differ. The 'dried' beam had the lowest in agreement with its larger beam displacement (Figure 5).

Jeronimidis and Parkyn (9) have shown that over these temperature excursions, significant tensile thermal strains can be built into the 90° ply of unbalanced $0^\circ/90^\circ$ beams. The cracks arise because either the thermal strain increases and/or the transverse strength decreases until the latter is exceeded. For the as-fabricated beam, the thermal strain increases more because the volatiles enhance the expansion

TABLE 1

Transverse crack densities determined by penetrant enhanced X-radiography in $0_2/90_2$ PMR-15 beams, subjected to 160 thermal cycles from $20\text{-}300^\circ\text{C}$ with 5 min dwell times.

Beam Condition	Crack Density/ m^{-1}
Dried	117
As-fabricated	274

Fig 4: Mass spectra of the volatiles desorbed at $\approx 400^{\circ}\text{C}$ from PMR-15 CFRP post-cured, (a) free of bagging films, (b) bagged up in the press-clave. Ion currents at 10^{-9}A . The clusters at 18 amu is for water, 28 amu methanol, 44 amu carbon dioxide and 66 amu cyclopentadiene (see ref 6 for details). Note the larger intensity of the 66 amu cluster for (b).

Fig 5: Changes in weight and displacement (δ) of a $0_2^{\circ}/90_2^{\circ}$ beam during thermal cycling. The as-post-cured beam (\circ, \bullet) and the dried beam ($\blacktriangle, \blacksquare$). NB The expanded scale up to 6 cycles.

coefficient of the matrix (6). As a result, there is a greater tendency for microcrack development. However, a thermal fatigue mechanism in the presence of volatiles has not been ruled out.

Drying the beam prior to thermal cycling leads to an enhancement of thermal strain because of the restrained matrix shrinkage associated with reverse of the matrix swelling. However the reduced temperature dependence of the expansion coefficient gives rise to a less rapid increase in thermal strain and a lower propensity to crack formation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Simultaneous thermogravimetric analysis with mass spectrometry has shown the presence of entrapped methanol and water in PMR-15 carbon fibre composites. Thermal degradation also involves the formation of cyclopentadiene, carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, water, methanol and other hydrocarbon fragments.

Post-curing the laminates enclosed in the bagging films entraps more volatiles and induces the less thermally stable but longer polycyclopentadiene crosslinks. During post-curing in the absence of these films, the rate of desorption of monomeric cyclopentadiene may lead to a variability in matrix crosslink density and thermomechanical response of the laminate, especially through the thickness (10). Complex changes in thermal strain caused by desorption/absorption of volatiles and an enhancement in expansion coefficient are responsible for the time-dependent transverse cracking during thermal cycling.

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6. REFERENCES

1. D. Wilson, *British Polymer Journal* 20 (1988), 405.
2. J.E. Bailey, P.T. Curtis, A. Parvizi, *Proc.Roy.Soc.Lond.* A366 (1979), 599.
3. F.R. Jones, M. Mulheron, J.E. Bailey, *J.Mater.Sci.* 18 (1983), 1522 and 1533.
4. G.A. Owens and S.E. Schofield, *Comp.Sci.Tech.* 33 (1988), 177.
5. D. Wilson, et al, *Sampe Conf. Proceedings*, Seattle 1986.
6. M. Simpson, P.M. Jacobs and F.R. Jones, *Composites*, in press.
7. T.A. Collings and D.E.W. Stone, *Composites* 16 (1985), 307.
8. F.S. Dainton and K.J. Ivin, *Quarterly Revs.* 12 (1958), 61.
9. G. Jeronimidis and R. Parkyn, *J.Comp.Mater.* 1988, 22, 401.
10. Z.D. Xiang and F.R. Jones, *Aspects of Thermal Degradation of PMR-15 Based Composites in Developments in Science and Technology of Composite Materials*, (Ed A.R. Bunsell et al), Elsevier, London, 1989, pp 595-601.

